

Vocational Evaluation: A Systematic Review of Outcomes Following Vocational Evaluation

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Federal legislation has shaped the provision of services to individuals with disabilities for years. For example, the Rehabilitation Act of 1973 (Rehabilitation Act of 1973, 1973) mandated federal funding to state vocational rehabilitation agencies to assist people with disabilities to find or maintain community employment through numerous vocational rehabilitation services (Colley & Jamison, 1998; Cozzens, Dowdy, & Smith, 1999; Dunham, Schrader, & Dunham, 2000; Gardner & Scott, 2001; Price-Ellingstad & Berry, 2000). Services offered via the Rehabilitation Act include but are not limited to assessment/evaluation, career guidance and counseling, and job placement services (Rehabilitation Services Administration, 2004). The eligibility for these services continues until the person with a disability is successfully employed for 90 days or has not made adequate progress toward employment. Another example is the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (2004), which mandates that youth ages 16 to 21 receive transition services to support progress towards positive post-school education, employment, and independent living outcomes. Services include instruction, community experiences, development of employment and other post-school adult living objectives, and functional vocational evaluation.

A common service offered, as a result of the different legislation, is vocational evaluation. Vocational evaluation can be defined as the systematic collection of data to determine an individual's work adjustment needs (Ahlers-Potentia al., 2003; Dowd, 1993; Herbert, Lorenz, & Trusty, 2010; Leconte & Neubert, 1997; Nadolsky, 1971; Pacinelli, 1970; Pruitt, 1977, 1986). Evaluation includes the collection of data on (a) individual strengths, preferences, and interests, (b) current and future demands of the workplace,

(c) work history, and (d) individual performance in the workplace. The focus of vocational evaluation is measurement of individual performance on actual job tasks or vocational skills in the natural environment where individuals would be performing these skills to determine an individual's (Herbert et al., 2010; Nadolsky, 1971; Bacinelli, 1970). Vocational evaluation is a very diverse field. The term itself is defined differently across the literature. As noted by Menz (1984) and Innes and Straker (1998), the terms *vocational assessment* and *vocational evaluation* continue to be used interchangeably in the literature. In fact, the two terms are viewed as synonyms (e.g., Stevenson & Lindberg, 2010). Castiglione, Leconte, and Smith (2018), in a position paper of the Interdisciplinary Council on Vocational Evaluation and Assessment, provide clarification regarding assessment and evaluation stating that vocational evaluation is a comprehensive process that incorporates multiple methods of assessment or data collection for the purpose of supporting an individual's development. For the purposes of this study, we will refer to the process as vocational evaluation. Many professions and professional groups administer vocational evaluations to a wide range of populations in various locations.

The most recent amendment of Title I of the Rehabilitation Act (1973) by Title IV of the Workforce Innovation and Opportunity Act (WIOA; Public Law 113–128) mandates under Part 361.4 – State Vocational Rehabilitation Services Programs conduct assessment for eligibility and vocational rehabilitation needs, such as assessment of (a) abilities, capabilities, and capacity to perform in work situations and work environments; (b) educational achievements; (c) strengths and interests; and (d) medical, psychiatric, psychological, and other pertinent vocational, educational, cultural, social, recreational, and environmental factors affecting employment and rehabilitation needs (State Vocational Rehabilitation Services Program, 2015). Unfortunately,

WIOA does not provide guidance on how to ethically and reliably measure these domains (e.g., assessment methods or protocols, instruments leading to empirically supported conclusions).

Many factors can influence the results of vocational evaluation, including, but not limited to, the type of assessment used, time the assessment was administered, and individual characteristics of clients (e.g., disability). While there is mixed evidence—Brickham, Kim, Gonzalez, and Rosenthal (2016) determined the receipt of assessment services was one of seven important predictors of competitive employment; Chan et al. (2008) determined the receipt of assessment services did not predict employment outcomes in the research literature regarding vocational evaluation—importance lies in the understanding of what role activities related to vocational evaluation play in providing job placement services to people with disabilities (Kluesner, Taylor, & Bordieri, 2005).

An effective practice is one that has been experimentally compared against another practice and shown to be significantly superior over the other. Vocational evaluation emerged as a practice in the late 1960s, which was before it was mandated by various legislations. Standards driving the practice evolved over a span of years (i.e., 1970 to 2003). Many practices commonly used in vocational evaluation have not been experimentally verified (e.g., use of picture interest inventories; Elksnin & Elksnin, 1990) or are seen as effective practices despite contrary empirical evidence (e.g., functional capacity evaluations; McFadden, MacDonald, Fogarty, Le, & Merritt, 2010). All codes of ethics (e.g., the American Counseling Association, 2014; American Psychological Association, 2018; Commission on Rehabilitation Counselor Certification, 2017; and National Association of Social Workers, 2018) require professionals to utilize research findings in their practices feelings and interests. Vocational evaluation professionals should be convinced their approaches

are in the best interest of other related professionals and their clients before using a practice. To best serve clients, vocational evaluation professionals should be able to identify approaches that have empirical support and are not likely to harm and/or mislead clients. Vocational evaluation professionals cannot fulfill these ethical and legal obligations unless they can recognize assessments and interventions that are valid and reliable in achieving the intended outcome, whether that be placement, identification of employment supports, or job retention (Thyer & Pignotti, 2015). In 2016, members of the Vocational Evaluation and Career Assessment Professionals Association (VECAP) raised questions about the empirical evidence supporting vocational assessment and evaluation. VECAP is a nonprofit organization promoting the professions and services of vocational evaluation and work adjustment, which was originally founded as the Vocational Evaluation and Work Adjustment Association (VEWAA) in 1967 (The Vocational Evaluation and Career Assessment Professionals Association, n.d. -a). The organization commissioned this review of the literature to gain a better understanding of what practices in vocational evaluation lead to positive employment outcomes.

Rowe, Mazzotti, Hirano, and Alverson (2015) outlined a process for evaluation that included (a) determining what to assess, (b) selecting appropriate assessments, (c) conducting assessments, (d) analyzing assessment results, and (e) using the assessment data. This process aligns with the vocational assessment process outlined in Ahlers et al. (2003; referral and planning, assessment and career exploration, follow-up and quality assurance). Rowe et al., 2015 noted there are a multitude of skills that can be assessed; however, the selection of assessment instruments or procedures is crucial to inform Vocational evaluation is a process that helps students /clients learn more about themselves, but more importantly, provides information that will guide services and supports to increase the

likelihood of positive employment outcomes (Rowe et al., 2015). Therefore, the purpose of this systematic review of the literature on vocational evaluation was to identify effective evaluation practices that lead to positive employment outcomes for individuals with disabilities.

Method

Search

Studies used to identify effective practices for vocational evaluation were identified by (a) conducting an initial electronic search of published research from 1949 to 2017, (b) reviewing reference lists and related articles, (c) reviewing historical white papers and conference proceedings (e.g., Vocational Evaluation and Work Association) published between the 1970s and 1980s, and (d) conducting hand searches of relevant journals such as

- *American Rehabilitation,*
- *Journal of Applied Rehabilitation Counseling,*
- *Journal of Career Assessment, Career Development and Transition for Exceptional Individuals,*
- *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation,*
- *Journal of Rehabilitation,*
- *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation,*
- *Rehabilitation Counseling Bulletin,*
- *The Career Development Quarterly,*
- *Vocational Evaluation and Career Assessment Professionals Association Journal,* and
- *Vocational Evaluation and Work Adjustment Bulletin.*

OneSearch, an electronic library search engine, was used to search the University Libraries' Catalog, subscribed journals, scholarly article databases, news, and popular publications on the

keywords entered. Databases included Alexander Street Press, American Chemical Society, American Economic Association, American Institute of Physics, American Medical Association, American Psychological Association, American Society of Civil Engineers, Annual Reviews, Association for Computing Machinery, Cambridge Scientific Abstracts, Cambridge University Press, Duke University Press, Elsevier, Emerald, Érudit, Facts On File, Gale, Geological Society of America, GPO, HathiTrust, Hindawi, IEEE, Institute of Physics, Johns Hopkins University Press (Project Muse), LexisNexis, Library of Congress (American Memory), Modern Language Association, National Agricultural Library, Nature Publishing Group, Naxos Music Library, Optical Society of America, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Oxford University Press, ProQuest, Royal Society of Chemistry, SAGE Publications, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, Taylor & Francis, Thieme, University of Chicago Press, Walter de Gruyter, and Wiley-Blackwell. The University Libraries' Catalog consisted of 76,000 physical print volumes, a combined 881,000 print and e-book titles, and 125,390 unique e-journal titles.

In addition, hard copies of all editions of the *Vocational Evaluation and Work Adjustment Association (VEWAA)* journal, conference proceedings related to VEWAA, and all editions of the *Vocational Evaluation and Career Assessment Professionals Association (VECAP)* journal were hand-searched. A search protocol of 82 pages of systematic two- and three-word combinations of 100 keywords was used to guide the search (see Appendix A). Full and truncated versions of search terms were used (e.g., employment assessment, employ*, assess*, evaluation, eval*, job-matching, job match*, vocational abilities assessment, workability assessment, employment readiness, individualized plan for employment, job adjustments, job adjust*). Keywords represented terms directly associated with evaluation (e.g., employment

assessment) as well as terms that may include evaluation as part of a process (e.g., job-matching), and terms associated with specific skills that might be assessed as part of vocational evaluation (e.g., employment readiness, work adjustment).

Inclusion Criteria

To be included in the review, articles needed to meet the following criteria: (a) published between 1949 and 2017; (b) included participants with disabling conditions (e.g., visual impairments, hearing impairments, mobility impairments, intellectual disabilities, learning disabilities, traumatic brain injury, mental illness); (c) included independent or dependent variables related to vocational evaluation and linked to employment outcomes (e.g., successful case closures, rates of competitive employment placements, and specific job placement activities; see Appendix B for list of 78 employment outcomes identified). Items that were within the search limits and appeared relevant (addressed above criteria based on title and short abstract alone) were stored in RefWorks, an online reference manager. The initial search of key terms resulted in 201,556 articles. Of those, approximately 1,500 were shortlisted for review of full title, abstract, and full-text review. The items were stored in RefWorks for critical appraisal. Following the search on OneSearch, the 1500 articles stored in RefWorks were re-examined for their relevance of the title and journal names, as well as long abstracts, which led to the inclusion of 590 articles. Examples of articles that were excluded because of unrelated content included articles published in languages other than English, articles on foreign populations or practices, conference proceedings, and articles that primarily evaluated or validated instruments used in vocational evaluation. Articles that were not electronically available through the database subscriptions of the University were retrieved through the interlibrary loan. All articles were converted into searchable PDF files and numbered and labeled in the order of their retrieval.

Then reference information was searched through RefWorks and other websites containing citation information. Next we examined the 590 potential articles more closely to ensure they included relevant information for this review. Of the 590 articles, 235 (40%) were quantitative and 355 (60%) were either descriptive or qualitative in nature. Of the 235 quantitative articles, 102 (43%) included relevant information for this review, and of the 355 qualitative articles, 302 (85%) included relevant information to inform this review.

All quantitative and qualitative articles were coded in NVivo 11 (<https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/home>), a qualitative data analysis software, where the information was clustered into themes as they emerged in the process. The quantitative articles were additionally coded using a coding form developed in Qualtrics (<https://www.qualtrics.com>), an online survey program, to capture the experimental data (e.g., independent variable, dependent variable, and results). A range of experimental and qualitative methods was used to examine the effects of vocational evaluation or an aspect of vocational evaluation on participant outcomes (e.g., independent group designs, repeated measures, focus groups, small *n* research, quasi-experimental designs, and program evaluations).

Results

The reliable prediction of positive vocational outcomes is very complex and involves many characteristics that typically are not subject to vocational evaluation. Although the research in this area is not sparse, much of the scholarly work lacks methodological rigor. A notable issue is that many of the studies identified in this review included multi-component interventions that included assessment and evaluation; however, they did not conduct component analysis to determine if evaluation alone was the determining factor of employment success (e.g., Baldwin & Brusco, 2011; Chan et al., 2008; Joshi, Bouck, & Maeda, 2012). In addition to evaluation being included in multi-component interventions, the execution of vocational evaluations was

not limited to vocational evaluators as some of the definitions and white papers suggest (Ahlers et al., 2003; CARF, 1996; Dowd, 1993; Nadolsky, 1971; Pacinelli, 1970; Pruitt, 1977, 1986; Sitlington & Clark, 2001; Smith et al., 1996; Vocational Evaluation and Work Adjustment Association, 1975). Several professions—for example, rehabilitation counselors, graduates of master programs in psychology, school psychologists, and rehabilitation psychologists with formal training in assessment and behavioral statistics—conducted vocational assessment/evaluations (e.g., Anderson & Hohenshil, 1990; Donoso, Hernandez, & Horin, 2010; Johnstone, Schopp, Harper, & Koscuilek, 1999; Luft, 2014; Tidwell, Fleming, Kraska, & Alderman, 2016), as well as professions with or without degree or formal training in evaluation and statistics (e.g., Agran & Morgan, 1991; Breeding, 2008; Dillahunt-Aspillaga et al., 2015; Morehouse & Albright, 1991; Rosenthal, Hursh, Lui, Isom, & Sasson, 2007).

Studies rarely addressed variables of vocational evaluation and tended to explain findings through a limited perspective, losing sight of the complexities of vocational evaluation. Lastly, studies regarding vocational evaluation lacked a conceptual model regarding how to investigate effects on competitive employment (i.e., immediate effects, effects across time). Research used in this review consisted of experimental, correlational, and qualitative methods. Findings regarding the impact of vocational evaluation were mixed and made it difficult to draw any discernable conclusions. Of the 102 quantitative articles, 17% ($n = 17$) provided supporting evidence for vocational evaluation, 20% ($n = 20$) provided partially supporting evidence, 26% ($n = 27$) provided no supporting evidence, and an additional 37% ($n = 38$) provided insufficient evidence to determine if vocational evaluation was a key factor. For example, some studies (e.g., Dean, Ashley, Schmidt, & Rowe, 2006; Oberoi, Balcazar, Suarez-Balcazar, Langi, & Lukyanova, 2015) reported vocational evaluation was a significant predictor of successful

employment outcomes. Others (e.g., Handelsman & Wurtz, 1971; Oswald, 2016) reported receipt of assessment services negatively predicted successful outcomes. Some studies reported that only sometimes evaluation led to positive employment outcomes (e.g., Capella, 2003), while other studies reported that vocational evaluation did not predict employment outcomes (e.g., Caston & Watson, 1990; Marut & Bullis, 1985; Schonbrun, Sales, & Kampfe, 2007; Tucker & Degeneffe, 2017). Although explanations of these results were not always explicitly stated, other studies reviewed provided some insight. For example, timing and duration of vocational evaluation was an explanation highlighted that could impact results, thus impacting recommendations (e.g., Brickham, Kim, Gonzalez, & Rosenthal, 2016; Cook, 1978; Stice & Moore, 2005). Another explanation included types of assessments used in vocational evaluation (e.g., Agran & Morgan, 1991; Grasso, Jitendra, Browder, & Harp, 2004; Kortering & Braziel, 2008; McCue, 1984). Therefore, these explanations could reasonably be attributing factors to the mixed results identified.

The experimental literature identified in this systematic review did not provide clear recommendations for effective practices in vocational evaluation. The breadth of information learned from the correlational and qualitative literature reviewed led to organization of our findings by aspects of the evaluation process as outlined in Ahlers et al. (2003) and further iterated by Rowe et al. (2015). Below is a summary of the results by the key components of an evaluation process as outlined in Rowe et al. (2015).

Determining What to Assess

The purpose of vocational evaluation is to gather information to help make decisions regarding support for individuals in obtaining and maintaining employment. As Rowe et al. (2015) stated, a comprehensive process would incl

perceptions, and performance of skill" (p. 30 of employment, hours worked, and/or wage), a concept identified by many others prior to Rowe (e.g., Ahlers et al., 2003; Herbert, Lorenz, & Trusty, 2010; Leconte & Neubert, 1997; Nadolsky, 1971). Interestingly, results of this review provided evidence of only a few skill domains explicitly listed in Workforce Innovation and Opportunity Act (e.g., work environments; intelligence and related functional capacities; work experience; State Vocational Rehabilitation Services Program, 2015).

Determining what to assess requires professionals to understand the demands of current and future employment opportunities. Potsubay and Frederickson (1985) suggested conducting a labor market analysis to determine skills needed in a particular career area. Understanding the expectations of current and future employment environments is critical in determining the gaps between what skills individuals have and what skills are needed to achieve a particular employment outcome. If the current or future career expectation is high levels of vocational performance, then Tsang, Lam, Ng, and Leung (2000) recommended assessing cognitive functioning, attitudes towards work, and work adjustment skills. If the expectation is related to skills, such as standing for long periods of time, lifting a certain amount of weight, then Zarate, Liberman, Mintz, and Massel (1998) recommended assessing an individual's physical capabilities. Taylor and Bond (2014) suggested that problem-solving skills should be assessed, as they relate to higher rates of employment.

Although not comprehensive, results of this review also revealed some areas of assessment specific to certain populations of individuals. For example, LeBlanc, Hayden, and Paulman (2000) indicated some areas important to assess when working with individuals with traumatic brain injury (TBI) included executive functioning skills, visual skills, and memory, as

these skills can impact performance on the job. Dillahunt-Aspillaga et al. (2015) expanded on this recommendation, suggesting vocational evaluation for clients with TBI should include different elements when measuring client domains (demographics, health history, educational history, work history, preinjury job performance, and success/failure of postinjury job trials), environmental elements (physical work environment, workplace culture, available supports and opportunities), and occupation/job requirements (description of job' physical, cognitive, and behavioral job demands; expectations, performance, and social responsibilities; and safety requirements).

Other studies that focused on individuals with more severe multiple disabilities suggested dexterity as a skill area to assess, especially if a potential employment opportunity required fine or gross motor skills (e.g., Rosenberg & Usdane, 1963). For individuals with autism spectrum disorder, previous literature recommended to assess adaptive living skills, as these are common skills in which this population has deficits and are required skills in many occupations (Hagner, Kurtz, May, & Cloutier, 2014). The assessment of intelligence and previous work experience was also deemed suitable for individuals with developmental disabilities, as these skills predict placement in either private employment or skilled training settings (Handelsman & Wurtz, 1971).

Selecting Appropriate Assessments

Once the skills needed to be successful in current and future working environments are identified, the next step is to find an assessment or data collection procedure that will measure that skill (Rowe et al., 2015). As an example, Gross et al. (2014) found data obtained from semi-structured functional interviews improved the level of sustained work compared to information obtained from performance-based functional capacity evaluations. As indicated by Castiglione et

al. (2018), the evaluation process should measure the individual, the environment, and the congruence between the two. The authors posit the theory that vocational assessment and evaluation consists of three levels of service intensity and comprehensiveness: (1) Screening or Needs Assessment, (2) Clinical or Exploratory, and (3) Vocational Evaluation. Each level has a different purpose and provides information to make decisions regarding obtaining and maintaining employment. The levels are not intended to be a menu of options but a framework for decision-making regarding additional information needed. If sufficient information is not garnered in the screening and referral process, then the Vocational Evaluator would move into the next level of evaluation (Ahlers et al., 2003). Although this review did not result in research exploring assessment levels as defined by VECAP, it revealed several assessment tools that were successful in measuring certain skills and could be used in each of the different levels (see Appendix C for an alphabetical list of 144 instruments identified in the quantitative literature). Although vocational evaluation includes other well-known procedures for collecting evaluation data (e.g., behavioral observation), Appendix C only includes examples of published assessment tools referenced in the quantitative literature. Some assessments listed may have been updated and newer versions may be available, and others may have been discontinued and are no longer in print/circulation.

As Rowe et al. (2015) stated, when determining which assessments are appropriate, a critical review of each assessment is necessary to identify whether the measure is valid and reliable, and appropriate for the intended population. This information improves confidence the results will assist in determining appropriate supports or services for individuals to obtain and maintain employment. The review furnished mixed evidence for the efficacy of vocational evaluation practices, hence, the limited number of measurement instruments identified. Even

though many measures (e.g., published assessment tools, behavioral observations, semi-structured interviews, environmental analysis) were used in the research and identified as playing a role in effective vocational assessment/evaluation, since many studies did not complete component analysis, discerning from the literature if the administration of any one assessment or combination of assessments resulted in positive employment outcomes was difficult.

Conducting Assessments

Rowe et al. (2015) suggested using a multidisciplinary approach to assessment and evaluation involving multiple people, over multiple days, and using multiple measures. The process for conducting assessments will differ based on what is being assessed and the data collection methods required. As VECAP pointed out, depending on the purpose, evaluation can vary (e.g., screening for eligibility, exploring vocational potential; The Vocational Evaluation and Career Assessment Professionals Association, n.d.-b). Although results of the review did not speak to the specific levels of assessment, the study yielded a few effective vocational evaluation practices. First, vocational evaluations that were repeatedly conducted over time in conjunction with vocational education or training related to successful outcomes (e.g., Estrada-Hernandez, Wadsworth, Nietupski, & Winslow, 2008). In addition, as noted in Rowe et al. (2015), findings indicated the use of multiple comprehensive assessments increased the ability to make reasonable career decisions among clients with various disabilities (McCabe, Sprong, Dallas, Mui, & Upton, 2013). As indicated in the literature, comprehensive vocational evaluations could include the Bender Visual-Motor Gestalt Test (BVMGT), Dial Behavior Rating Scale, Emotional Behavior Checklist, Haptic Visual Discrimination Test (HVDT), McCarron Assessment of Neuromuscular Development (MAND), O*NET Ability Profiler (AP)–Parts 1 to 11,

O*NET Career Interest Inventory, O*NET Career Values Inventory, Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT), Picture Inventory Career Survey, Personality Assessment Inventory (PAI), 16 PF General Form, Sixteen Personality Factors (16PF)–Form E, Stanford Test of Achievement (SAT), Street Survival Skills Questionnaire (SSSQ), Wide Range Achievement Test 3 (WRAT-3)–Arithmetic, Wide Range Achievement Test 4 (WRAT-4), Woodcock Johnson III–Achievement, and Woodcock Johnson III–Cognitive Abilities.

Analyzing and Using the Evaluation Data

Analyzing and using evaluation data is probably one of the most critical steps in the vocational evaluation process (Ahlers et al., 2003; Rowe et al., 2015). As evidenced in this review, the act of conducting the evaluation and drawing employment-related conclusions from the results does not necessarily lead to successful employment outcomes. The interpretation and use of the information will determine the quality and kind of outcomes (Essig and Kelly, 2013), along with other previous research, indicated assessments should not be used to obtain data from clients; rather, data should be used as an educational tool to improve vocational outcomes in rehabilitation. Essig and Kelly concluded that transactional feedback that mirrors self-views of clients and addresses discrepant information enhances the ability to make career decisions. As Rowe et al. (2015) stated, evaluation data can be used to determine employment goals, present levels of performance, appropriate services and supports, and instruction on the job. Results of this review identified several instances in which the decisions made based on evaluation data led to positive outcomes. For example, results of observations and job try-outs contributed to correct employment recommendation and/or placements by vocational evaluators or secondary transition program personnel among vocational rehabilitation clients and students

from a community rehabilitation provider (Miller, 1958) or secondary transition program (Schall et al., 2015).

One important theme identified in the literature was the need for adequate training in the evaluation process. Some publishers of measurement instruments relevant to vocational evaluation—for example, Pearson Education (2018)—have minimum educational qualification requirements for the purchase of measurement instruments assessing human functioning. Pearson Education's instruments are divided into three categories that limit the purchase of instruments, which implies the use of the instruments by the same person who purchased them. Some instruments do not require educational qualifications; however, others require specific master's degrees or memberships in organizations related to the use of instruments. The remaining instruments require specific doctorates and licensure or certification also related to the use of these instruments. Persons conducting vocational evaluation must ensure they use instruments for which they possess the required level of formal academic education and/or instrument-related licensure and certification. Administering those assessments that require certain certifications or qualifications without appropriate training could result in inaccurate analysis and use of data (Taylor, Bordieri, Crimando, & Janikoski, 1993).

The use of results from functional vocational evaluation contributed to improved development and delivery of employment placement-oriented services for people with disabilities (Vandergoot, 1987). Participants who were actively involved in their vocational evaluations were able to better understand their strengths and skills and the implications for occupational choice based on results of vocational evaluation using the Career Decision Scale, Vocational Self Awareness, and the Employability Maturity Vocational Interview (Farley, Bolton, & Parkerson, 1992). Using data on an ongoing basis from intensified

vocational services (ongoing functional assessments including work interests and needs, and capacity for work) can lead to sustained, competitive employment of people with severe mental illness and other risk factors (Ahrens, Frey, & Burke, 1999).

Discussion

This review defines vocational evaluation as a collaborative, inter-professional process of evaluating work goals, abilities, functions, tolerances, and limitations of people with and without disabilities to (a) gain an understanding of their work-related strengths and deficits; (b) determine whether employment or occupations are consistent with their work goals, abilities, functions, tolerances, and limitations; and (c) make recommendations of support necessary to achieve work goals and work in suitable employment or occupations for more extended periods (Dillahunt-Aspillaga et al., 2015; Dowd, 1993; Strauser, Chan, Wang, Wu, & Rahimi, 2014). As mentioned previously, discerning from the literature the magnitude of impact that vocational evaluation alone has on employment outcomes is difficult; however, findings indicated that when appropriate assessments are selected and administered, the data could be useful in determining appropriate job placements and other employment supports.

Limitations and Implications for Future Research

There are several limitations to this systematic review. First, this review resulted in mixed evidence regarding the relationship between vocational evaluation and employment outcomes. Many studies reported the effects of vocational evaluation as a component of a larger intervention that included other services delivered, which made discerning whether vocational evaluation was what contributed to positive employment outcomes was difficult. Some studies looked only at the relationship between vocational evaluation and employment outcomes, resulting in very different results. The literature is unclear as to why there are such discrepancies, but one might assume it has to do with the complexity of employment outcomes or the lack of

flexibility in the evaluation process. Employment outcomes are often impacted by characteristics that are not subject to vocational evaluation and are sometimes difficult to control in a research study. Future research on vocational evaluation should exclusively examine magnitude of impacts of vocational evaluation on specific employment outcomes and attempt to control statistically for demographic or other factors that could influence employment outcomes. Also, time and cost are some of the variables that impact an evaluator's ability to individualize the evaluation process. Also consumers are forced to fit a one-size-fits-all evaluation process, then a restricted range of recommendations will be forced to fit every consumer" (p. 49). The nature and extent of a influence the content of the evaluation; therefore, the attempt to standardized the evaluation process in many of the studies reviewed could have impacted the employment outcomes of participants.

Although some studies included in this review were based on statistics and/or logic and can help inform causal inferences (Thompson, Diamond, McWilliam, Snyder, & Snyder, 2005), results of this review are limited because many studies included research designs in which causality cannot be conferred (e.g., qualitative, correlational). Future research must employ high quality experimental designs that collect longitudinal data on the effects of vocational evaluation if causal conclusions about the effects of vocational evaluation are to be made. A third limitation of this review is the focus on vocational evaluation in general and not specific types of vocational assessment or outcomes disaggregated by demographic characteristics (e.g., disability, gender, ethnicity). Future research could disaggregate data by different demographic characteristics to identify specific evaluation practices that lead to more specific employment outcomes (e.g., obtaining a job, maintaining a job, wage, benefits).

In addition, future empirical investigations should be used to verify whether the practical application of the theory of three levels and the distinction between vocational assessments and vocational evaluation would lead to better vocational outcomes relative to the current status quo of vocational assessment without levels. The identification of instruments that produce useable results that possess empirically validated relationships with occupational outcomes appears more beneficial for clients than using subjective choices of instruments with unknown or assumed psychometric and biometric properties in vocational assessment. Therefore, the literature is unclear whether levels of assessment would ensure useable results in each of the 16 assessment domains named by WIOA (State Vocational Rehabilitation Services Program, 2015).

Lastly, the findings of this systematic review may not reflect what is happening in the field. As with many professions, we know that careful planning and delivery of evaluation is happening; however, systematic investigation of that process is limited. There remains a need to continue to identify effective vocational evaluation practices. The lack of empirically supported vocational evaluation practices identified to assess across all the domains legislated in the WIOA indicates that vocational evaluators and other professionals conducting vocational evaluation have limited number of evaluation tools to support effectively clients in obtaining and maintaining appropriate employment placements.

Recommendations for Future Practice

Many measures used in vocational evaluation identified in this review did not measure variables that we know from research do predict employment outcomes (e.g., social skills, career awareness skills, self-determination skills). Many of the measures identified in this review did not assess skills but rather characteristics of an individual (e.g., neuropathology, severity of illness, use of neuroleptic drugs, age at first hospitalization, biological vulnerability, family

psychiatric history, pre-treatment duration of illness, social class). Others assessed skill or functioning that could impact employment outcomes (e.g., ego strength/functioning, ability to get along or function socially with others, ego strength or self-concept in the role of worker, work adjustment skills). In future practice, practitioners should spend time considering what to assess before selecting assessments so that the information obtained is easily used to make decisions regarding employment placement and maintenance for the individual. Not all individuals will require the same battery of assessments. As Ahlers et al. (2003) recognized, most professionals conducting vocational evaluations have a general process for evaluation to meet consumer needs (e.g., disability type, goals, referral questions) and there is opportunity to use a variety of evaluation instruments or procedures (e.g., interviews, standardized assessments, situational assessments, observations). To yield more valid and useful results and maximize employment outcomes, Ahlers and colleagues recommend tailoring the evaluation process to the individual. A one-size-fits-all approach will restrict the range of employment recommendations made for an individual (i.e., range of recommendations will reflect the scope of the process rather than the individual).

A second recommendation for practice is to select appropriate instruments or data collection methods that have adequate evidence of validity and reliability. The field of vocational evaluation should establish a set of standards with defined sets of instruments or methods with adequate psychometric or biometric properties for each assessment domain identified in WIOA (e.g., educational achievement, interests, interpersonal skills, personal social adjustments) like other professions (e.g., rehabilitation psychology, clinical psychology, school psychology, physical therapy, occupational therapy). Vocational evaluation has assessment descriptions as found in various definitions and white papers, but many times, the process relies solely on

professional judgment and conclusions drawn from results of evaluation instruments without, or with inadequate, psychometric or biometric properties (e.g., picture interest inventories; Elksnin & Elksnin, 1990). Conclusions of vocational evaluation determine vocational outcomes, as well as eligibility for and types of rehabilitation of services. The definition of concrete assessment standards and formal guidance on the selection of instruments with adequate psychometric or biometric properties for each assessment area that WIOA mandates would advance the field of vocational assessment/evaluation.

Lastly, this review resulted in the identification of 89 professions and professional groups conducting vocational evaluation. Although some professionals (i.e., vocational evaluators) are recognized by professional certification (i.e., Certified Vocational Evaluation Specialist) and possess unique sets of knowledge and skills to conduct vocational evaluations, the role of a vocational evaluator is expanding (Ahlers et al., 2003). As Ahlers and colleagues point out, professionals conducting vocational evaluation are responsible for not just gathering information but synthesizing multiple sources of data (e.g., medical, psychological, educational, vocational) and sharing with a multidisciplinary team to then develop the best possible plan to achieve positive employment outcomes. Therefore, one recommendation is that all professionals conducting vocational evaluation have appropriate preparation to carry out adequately the evaluation process. Evidence for the applicability of the levels of assessment/evaluation as described in some definitions of vocational evaluation did not emerge in the review. Additional empirical research is needed to confirm the levels of vocational assessment (i.e., Screening or Needs Assessment, Clinical or Exploratory, and Vocational Evaluation) and distinguish between vocational assessment and vocational evaluation, as described in the position paper of the Interdisciplinary Council on Vocational Evaluation and Assessment (Castiglione et al., 2018).

Professional development is then needed to ensure professionals conducting vocational evaluation are adequately prepared to determine appropriate evaluation procedures, including identification of measures to address the requirements outlined in WIOA and meet the needs of clients. Domain-specific approaches to vocational evaluation may have to be defined, and subsequent training could be rendered that includes the use of reliable and valid instruments normed for the specific populations, subject to specific evaluations and/or the use of less formal approaches (behavioral observations, structured interviews) that lead to more valid conclusions for individual clients. Training should also focus on these specific evaluations procedures that predict vocational outcomes in a specific assessment domain. Training should also include the awareness of instruments that will likely render useless data or data unrelated to vocational outcomes. Lastly, training on data interpretation in each of the 16 domains will be beneficial for those who make impactful decisions that determine the eligibility for rehabilitation services and the vocational future of clients of vocational evaluation.

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Appendix A

Keywords Used in the Systematic Search

Number	Keyword	Number	Keyword
1	ability-to-work assessment	51	potential for employment
2	absence/s	52	practice
3	accident/s	53	pre-work assessment
4	assessment	54	randomized controlled trial/s
5	back to work	55	ready for employment
6	career assessment/s	56	reasonable accommodation/s
7	career interest/s	57	reemployment assessment
8	disability/ies	58	resume/ing employment
9	disabled	59	resuming work
10	divorce/e/es/s	60	retain/ing employment
11	divorced/ing	61	retain/ing job
12	employability	62	retain/ing work
13	employability analysis	63	return/ed/ing to work
14	employability assessment	64	RTW
15	employed	65	sick
16	employment plan	66	spouse
17	employment potential	67	transition
18	employment program	68	vocational
19	employment provision/s	69	vocational abilities assessment
20	employment readiness	70	vocational analysis
21	employment resumption	71	vocational appraisal

22	employment retention	72	vocational assessment/s
23	evaluation	73	vocational evaluation specialist
24	find/ing/found employment	74	vocational evaluation/s
25	find/ing/found work	75	vocational evaluator
26	fit for employment	76	vocational expert
27	forensic rehabilitation	77	vocational rehab
28	hired/ing	78	vocational rehabilitation
29	ill	79	vocational specialist
30	illness/es	80	vocational/employability analysis
31	in employment	81	work ability assessment
32	individualized plan for employment	82	work absence/s
33	injured on job	83	work accident/s
34	injured on the job	84	work accommodation/s
35	injured worker/s	85	work injury/ies
36	injury/ies	86	work leave
37	IPE	87	work re-entry/reentry
38	job accommodation/s	88	work rehab
39	job adjustment/s	89	work rehabilitation
40	job modification/s	90	work resume
41	job placement	91	work resumption
42	job re-entry/reentry	92	work retention
43	job resumption	93	work return
44	job retention	94	workability assessment
45	job-matching assessment	95	workers' compensation
46	job-preference assessment	96	workplace accommodation/s

47	leave	97	workplace adjustment/s
48	litigation/s	98	workplace assessment
49	marriage	99	workplace modification/s
50	married	100	workplace rehabilitation

Appendix B

Summaries of Employment Outcomes Found in the Non-qualitative Literature

Number	Employment Outcomes
1	Ability of the McCarron-Dial System to predict employment and wages earned (J. A. Cook & Razzano, 1994)
2	Accessibility of vocational rehabilitation programs and services (Lombard, Hazelkorn, & Neubert, 1992)
3	Accuracy of the prognosis of client vocational potential (Holbert & Walker, 1973)
4	Accuracy of vocational evaluation recommendations (Rosenberg & Usdane, 1963)
5	Accuracy of vocational evaluation recommendation for employment six months after the termination of programs (Miller, 1958)
6	Accuracy of vocational evaluation recommendations for predicting employability (Hallenbeck & Campbell, 1975)
7	Career assessment practice (Herbert et al., 2010)
8	Career decision self-efficacy and work locus of control as indicators of vocational self-empowerment (Breeding, 2008)
9	Career thoughts (Strauser, Lustig, Keim, Ketz, & Malesky, 2002)
10	Case closures and amounts of weekly earnings (McCue, 1984)
11	Changes in weekly earnings (Growick & Stueland, 1979)
12	Commitment to career choice (Merz & Szymanski, 1997)
13	Congruence among vocational evaluation employment recommendation, vocational skills training, and employment outcome (Kosciulek, Prozonic, & Bell, 1995)
14	Determination of assessment, training, and placement (Bond & Dincin, 1986)
15	Determination of concepts in an instrument measuring employment outcomes (Thomas, Menz, & Rosenthal, 2001)
16	Determination of eligibility of clients with developmental disabilities (Roessler, Schriener, & Troxell, 1990)
17	Determination of the chance of re-incarceration (Griller Clark, Mathur, & Holding, 2011)
18	Domains of transition services (Luft, 2014)
19	Effectiveness of training recommendations (D. W. Cook, 1978)
20	Effectiveness of vocational rehabilitation recommendations (D. W. Cook, 1977)
21	Effectiveness of vocational rehabilitation services (Rogers, Anthony, Lyass, & Penk, 2006)
22	Effects of ecological versus standardized vocational assessment reports (Grasso, Jitendra, Browder, & Harp, 2004)
23	Effects of rehabilitation programs (Baldwin & Brusco, 2011)
24	Employment earnings among youth and younger adults with disabilities (Hemmeter, 2014)
25	Employment earnings and post-school outcomes (Izzo, Cartledge, Miller, Growick, & Rutkowski, 2000)

26	Employment outcomes and employment matching specific or general vocational interest (Tango & Kolodinsky, 2004)
27	Employment outcomes for African American and Caucasian women (Oberoi, Balcazar, Suarez-Balcazar, Langi, & Lukyanova, 2015)
28	Extent to which students with mild intellectual disability participated in vocational transition activities (Joshi et al., 2012)
29	Frequency of measurement instrument use (Donoso et al., 2010)
30	Implications for vocational preparation and occupational choice (Farley et al., 1992)
31	Insights regarding transition practices and processes, knowledge of transition assessments, and perception of needed training and technical assistance on transition assessments (Tidwell et al., 2016)
32	Job placement outcomes and employer satisfaction (Bolton & Brookings, 1991)
33	Level of career maturation (McCabe et al., 2013)
34	Measurement of workability after injury (Fadyl, Mcpherson, Schlüter, & Turner-Stokes, 2010)
35	Perceived status of career ambitions and readiness to make career decisions (Kortering & Braziel, 2008)
36	Perception of Internet use in vocational rehabilitation (Boeltzig, 2011)
37	Person-centered transition planning and the levels of functional behavior (Hagner et al., 2014)
38	Piece rate performances and actual vocational program levels (Gannaway, Sink, & Becket, 1980)
39	Placement into competitive employment (Capella, 2003; Gamble & Moore, 2003; Yankowitz & Musante, 1994)
40	Placement practices (Vandergoot, 1987)
41	Rates of program completion and successful closures (J. A. Cook et al., 2007)
42	Prediction of competitive employment (Adelman, Spitznagel, & Saxon, 1997; Boutin, 2011; Chan et al., 2008; Chronister et al., 2008; Kaya et al., 2016; Oswald, 2016; Strauser et al., 2010; Tucker & Degeneffe, 2017)
43	Prediction of employability, adjustment training placements, and competitive employment placements (Berven & Maki, 1979)
44	Prediction of employment and skilled training placements (Handelsman & Wurtz, 1971)
45	Prediction of occupational congruency between the types of pre- and post-injury employment (Dunn, 2001)
46	Prediction of enhanced job satisfaction (Rounds, 1990)
47	Prediction of successful job placements and work adjustments (Potsabay & Frederickson, 1985)
48	Prediction of trainability and job proficiency (Brown & Ghiselli, 1952; Ghiselli, 1949)
49	Prediction of vocational skills and outcomes with the Griffith Work Behavior Scale (Rogers, Anthony, Cohen, & Davies, 1997)
50	Prediction of wages as vocational outcomes (Sears, Wickizer, & Schulman, 2014)

51	Predictive abilities of neuropsychological evaluation results on successful employment (Johnstone et al., 1999)
52	Predictive differences among vocational evaluations that include paper-and-pencil intelligence, interests, and aptitude tests; work behavior evaluations, and the combination of both vocational and work behavior evaluations on vocational outcomes (Myers & Dagley, 1996)
53	Rates of competitive employment placements (Gowdy, Carlson, & Rapp, 2003)
54	Recurring concerns and the ideal make-up of One-Stop career centers (Zarate et al., 1998)
55	Rate of employment (Brickham et al., 2016; Schonbrun, Sales, & Kampfe, 2007)
56	Rate of successful case closure due to employment (Ahrens et al., 1999)
57	Rates of employment and training (Bond & Friedmeyer, 1987)
58	Rate of competitive employment (Ottomanelli, Barnett, Goetz, & Toscano, 2015)
59	Rehabilitation counseling expectations, preferences, and anticipations relating to the services provided by state vocational rehabilitation agencies (Koch, 2001)
60	Rehabilitation outcome (Marut & Bullis, 1985)
61	Relationship between certain socioeconomic variables and depression among injured workers (Stice & Moore, 2005)
62	Relationship between the level of functioning and vocational (i.e., transitional or competitive employment) and residential outcomes (J. A. Cook, Razzano, & Cappelleri, 1996)
63	Relationship between work samples and vocational choice upon completion of vocational evaluations (Gannaway & Sink, 1978)
64	Relationships among neuropsychological instruments, tailored cognitive situational evaluations, and judgments about future employability (LeBlanc et al., 2000)
65	Relationships between demographic, psychological, and vocational information, and vocational outcomes (D. W. Cook & Brookings, 1980)
66	Relationships between the provision of vocational evaluations and vocational outcomes (Caston & Watson, 1990)
67	Satisfaction with vocational evaluation services (Nalven, Oursler, Green, & Cordeiro, 2005)
68	Screening decisions on vocational potential after interviews, psychological testing, and a series of work samples (Roessler & Boone, 1982)
69	Specific job placement activities (Kluesner et al., 2005)
70	Successful case closures (Heinemann, Moore, Lazowski, Huber, & Semik, 2014; Peters, Scalia, & Fried, 1993)
71	Time to employment, hours worked, and income earned (LePage et al., 2016)
72	Training needs in community-based vocational assessment and adjustment services provided by professionals employed in rehabilitation and rehabilitation-related human services programs (Kelley, 1993)
73	Transition services that use vocational evaluation (Repetto, White, & Snauwaert, 1990)
74	Use of standardized instruments to screen for substance use disorders (Sprong, Dallas, Melvin, & Koch, 2014)

75	Vocational capacity of people with psychiatric disabilities (Anthony & Jansen, 1984)
76	Vocational performance of people with psychiatric disabilities (Tsang et al., 2000)
77	Vocational rehabilitation outcomes (Walls, Moore, Batiste, & Loy, 2009)
78	Working in competitive employment or matching vocational interest (Estrada-Hernandez et al., 2008)

Appendix C

Sample Assessments Identified in Review

Assessment	Skills Assessed	Population	Supporting Reference
Adaptive Behavior Assessment Scale II (ABAS-II)	Adaptive behavior	Autism spectrum disorder	Hagner et al. (2014)
Adaptive Behavior Assessment System (ABAS)	Adaptive behavior	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Addiction Severity Index (ASI)	Functioning (medical employment, drug use, alcohol use, legal, family/social, and psychological)	Methadone users	Coviello, Zanis, Wesnoski, and Domis (2009)
Armed Services Vocational Aptitude	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Alcohol Use Disorder and Associated Disabilities Interview Schedule-DSM-IV (AUDADIS-IV)	Substance abuse and anxiety disorders	Depression	Chen, Samet, Gorroochurn, and O'Hara (2016)
Bateria Woodcock-Munoz	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI)	Symptomatology	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Beck Depression Inventory (BDI)	Symptomatology, depression	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Coviello et al. (2009); Donoso et al. (2010)
Beck Depression Inventory – Second Edition (BDI-II)	Depression	Injured workers	Stice and Moore (2005)
Beery-Buktenica Developmental Test of Visual Motor Integration	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Behavior Rating Scale (BRS)	Sensory functioning	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Bender Visual-Motor Gestalt Test (BVMGT)	Program effectiveness, sensory	Various disabilities, psychiatric disabilities and	Donoso et al. (2010); Fortune and Eldredge

	functioning, neuropsychological functioning	alcoholism, vocational rehabilitation clients	(1982); McCabe et al. (2013)
Beta IQ	IQ to determine vocational potential	Physical disability	D. W. Cook and Brookings (1980)
Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS)	Symptomatology	Psychiatric disabilities (schizophrenia; affective disorder; schizoaffective disorder; bipolar disorder; major depressive disorder; anxiety, personality, paranoid, or dystemic disorders	Rogers et al. (1997); Rogers et al. (2006)
Buschke Selective Reminding Test (BSRT)	Memory	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
California Personality Inventory	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Career Assessment Inventory (CAI)	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Career Decision Scale (CDS)	Career indecisiveness	Orthopedic disabilities, other medical disabilities, mental retardation, psychiatric disorders, and sensory disorders	Farley et al. (1992)
Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale (CDSE) or Career Decision-Making Self-Efficacy Scale (CDMSE) (unclear from article)	Self-understanding and empowerment	Not identified	Breeding (2008)
Career Planning Scale (CPS)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Career Thoughts Inventory (CTI)	Career thoughts, readiness for career and employment decision making	Psychiatric disorders (depression, anxiety, bi-polar, schizophrenia) and Dual diagnosis of	Strauser et al. (2002); Strauser, Zanskas, and Lustig (2011)

		physical and psychiatric impairment, chronic medical conditions, mobility and orthopedic impairments, psychiatric disorder and alcohol and substance abuse, hearing or visual impairments, mental retardation and learning disability, cognitive disability, orthopedic impairments, TBI, and multiple disabilities	
Change Assessment Scale (CAS)	Readiness for change	Major psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia, affective disorder, & schizoaffective disorder)	Rogers et al. (2006)
Continuous Visual Memory Test (CVMT)	Memory	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Crawford Small Parts Dexterity Test (CSPDT)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Dementia Rating Scale	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Dial Behavior Rating Scale	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Differential Aptitude Tests (DAT)	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Ecological Assessments	Expectations of environment	Not identified	Grasso et al. (2004)
Emotional Behavior Checklist	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Employability Maturity Interview (EMI)	Vocational maturity	Orthopedic disabilities, other medical disabilities, mental retardation,	Farley et al. (1992)

		psychiatric disorders, and sensory disorders	
Employment Assessment Survey (EAS)	Factors related to employment (employment situation, educational achievement, job-related activities used to secure employment, perceived barriers to employment reported motivation, and confidence in finding and retaining work)	Methadone users	Coviello et al. (2009)
Escala de Inteligencia Wechsler para Adultos	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Fine motor (FM)	Motor functioning	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Finger Tapping Test	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Gates-MacGinitie Reading Tests (GMRT)	Reading comprehension	Youth and adults with learning disabilities	McCue (1984)
Geist Picture Interest Inventory (GPII)	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
General Aptitude Test Battery (GATB)	Functional capacity for work	Physical and developmental disabilities	Potsubay and Frederickson (1985)
Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Machamer, Temkin, Fraser, Doctor, and Dikmen (2005)
Global Assessment Scale (GAS)	Cognitive functioning	Mental illness	J. A. Cook et al. (1996)
Griffith Work Behavior Scale	Work skills	Psychiatric disabilities (schizophrenia; bipolar disorder or Major depressive disorder; anxiety,	Rogers et al. (1997)

		personality, paranoid, or dysthymic disorders	
Grooved Pegboard Test (GPT)	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Gross motor (GM)	Motor functioning	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Halstead Reitan Battery (HRB)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Halstead Reitan Neuropsychological Test Battery (Tactual Performance Test, Finger Oscillation Test, Aphasia Screening Test, Trail Making Test, Seashore Rhythm Test, Sensory Perceptual Examination, Speech Sounds Perception Test, Grip Strength) (HRNB)	Neuropsychological functioning	Learning disabilities	McCue (1984)
Haptic Visual Discrimination Test (HVDT)	Sensory functioning, program effectiveness	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism, various disabilities	Fortune and Eldredge (1982); McCabe et al. (2013)
Individual Worker Trait Rating Form (IWTRF)	Work behavior	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL)	Perceptions of social support	Major psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia, affective disorder, & schizoaffective disorder)	Rogers et al. (2006)
IPS Fidelity Scale	Quality and consistency of adherence to the IPS principles	Spinal cord injury	Ottomanelli et al. (2015)
Jewish Employment & Vocational Service (JEVS) - Work Samples	Work samples	Vocational rehabilitation clients with various disabilities and substance abuse disorder	Berven and Maki (1979)

Kaufman Adolescent and Adult Intelligence Test (KAIT)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational Rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test (KBIT)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Kaufman Test of Educational Achievement (K-TEA)	Achievement	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Lehman Quality of Life Interview (QOLI)	Quality of life	Major psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia, affective disorder, & schizoaffective disorder)	Rogers et al. (2006)
Letter Cancellation Task	Visual skills	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Line Bisection Test	Visual skills	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
McCarron Assessment of Neuromuscular Development (MAND)	Program effectiveness, motor functioning	Psychiatric disabilities and alcoholism, various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
McCarron-Dial System (MDS)	Sheltered work behaviors, work samples	Psychiatric disorders and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Mental Status Exam (MSE)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Millon Clinical Multiaxial Inventory (MCMI)	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Multilingual Aphasia Examination (MAE)	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Minnesota Importance Questionnaire (MIQ)	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI)	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
My Vocational Situation (MVS)	Confidence in one's vocational decision	Chronic medical conditions, mobility and orthopedic impairments, psychiatric disorder and alcohol and substance abuse, hearing or visual impairments,	Farley et al. (1992); Strauser et al. (2011)

		mental retardation and learning disability, cognitive disability, orthopedic impairments, TBI, and multiple disabilities, orthopedic disabilities, other medical disabilities, mental retardation, psychiatric disorders, and sensory disorders	
Non-reading Aptitude Test Battery	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Observational-Emotional Inventory (OEI)	Sensory functioning	Psychiatric disorders and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
O*NET Ability Profiler (AP)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
O*NET Career Interest Inventory	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
O*NET Career Values Inventory	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Paced Auditory Serial Addition Test (PASAT)	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT)	Verbal-cognitive functioning, program effectiveness	Psychiatric disorders and alcoholism, various disabilities	Fortune and Eldredge (1982); McCabe et al. (2013)
Peabody Individual Achievement Test	Reading comprehension	Learning disabilities	McCue (1984)
Personality Assessment Inventory (PAI)	Personality, program effectiveness	Vocational rehabilitation clients and people with various disabilities	Donoso et al. (2010); Fortune and Eldredge (1982); McCabe et al. (2013)
Picture Inventory Career Survey	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Program Satisfaction Survey	Satisfaction with vocational evaluation services	Orthopedic disabilities, other medical disabilities, mental retardation, psychiatric	Farley et al. (1992)

		disorders, and sensory disorders	
Projective Drawings	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Purdue Pegboard Test	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Raven's Progressive Matrices (APM & SPM)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational Rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Risk Assessment Battery (RAB)	Sex and drug risk factors	Methadone users	Coviello et al. (2009)
Rorschach Inkblot Test	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale	Self-esteem	Major psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia, affective disorder, & schizoaffective disorder)	Rogers et al. (2006)
Rotter Incomplete Sentences Blank (RISB)	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Self-Directed Search (SDS)	Vocational aptitude and interest, self-understanding and empowerment	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Breeding (2008); Donoso et al. (2010)
Self-Directed Search Form R (SDS-R)	Career decision-making readiness	Youth with disabilities at risk of failing or not completing high school	Kortering and Braziel (2008)
SF-12v2	Physical and mental health	Individuals with depression	Chen et al. (2016)
Singer Vocational Evaluation System (VES)	Job retention, work samples	Vocational rehabilitation clients with various disabilities	Gannaway et al. (1980)
Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire (16PF)	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)

Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire – Form E (16PF)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Sixteen Personality Factor Questionnaire – General Form	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Standardized Assessment of Work Behavior	Work behavior	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Myers and Dagley (1996)
Stanford Achievement Test (SAT)	Achievement	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Stanford Test of Academic Skills (TASK)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Stanford-Binet Intelligence Scales (SB)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Street Survival Skills Questionnaire (SSSQ)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Strong Campbell Inventory	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Strong Interest Inventory (SII)	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Structured work evaluations	Work capacity	Not identified	Anthony and Jansen (1984)
Student Styles Questionnaire (SSQ)	Career decision-making readiness	Youth with disabilities at risk of failing or not completing high school	Kortering and Braziel (2008)
Substance Abuse in Vocational Rehabilitation Screener (SAVR-S)	Substance abuse disorder	Various disabilities	Heinemann et al. (2014)
Survey of Vocational Rehabilitation Preferences and Anticipations (SVRPA)	Rehabilitation preferences and anticipations	Vocational rehabilitation clients with various disabilities	Koch (2001)
Symptom Checklist-90 (SCL-90)	Symptomatology	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Tendency to Foreclose scale (TTFS) - subscale of the Commitment to Career Choices Scale	Tendency to foreclose	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Merz and Szymanski (1997)

Test of Nonverbal Intelligence (TONI)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Testing, Orientation and Work Evaluation in Rehabilitation (TOWER) system	Hand dexterity and vocational aptitude	Severe disabilities	Rosenberg and Usdane (1963)
Thematic Apperception Test (TAT)	Personality	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Threshold Level of Independent Living Scale	Cognitive functioning	Mental illness	J. A. Cook et al. (1996)
Time Sample Behavioral Checklist (TSBC)	Appropriate and inappropriate behaviors	Psychiatrically impaired individuals with psychotic or nonpsychotic disorders	Massel et al. (1990)
Token Test	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Total motor (TM)	Motor functioning	Psychiatric disorders and alcoholism	Fortune and Eldredge (1982)
Trail-Making Test (TMT)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Trail-Making Test (TMT), Parts A and B	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Johnstone et al. (1999); Machamer et al. (2005)
Training Needs in Vocational Evaluation and Work Adjustment for Community Integration (TNVE)	Training needs and work adjustment	Clients with severe disabilities and complex special needs	Kelley (1993)
U.S. Employment Services	Vocational aptitude and interest	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Various aptitude and interests tests	Work adjustment	Physical or cognitive disabilities	Potsubay and Frederickson (1985)
Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales (VABS)	Adaptive behavior	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Visual Naming	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)

Vocational Exploration and Commitment scale (VECS) - subscale of the Commitment to Career Choices Scale	Vocational exploration and commitment	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Merz and Szymanski (1997)
Vocational Identity - subscale of the My Vocational Situation (MVS)	Vocational identity	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Merz and Szymanski (1997)
Vocational Self-Awareness Scale (VSA)	Vocational self-awareness	Orthopedic disabilities, other medical disabilities, mental retardation, psychiatric disorders, and sensory disorders	Farley et al. (1992)
Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence (WASI)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS)	IQ, cognitive functioning	Youth and adults with learning disabilities, vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010); McCue (1984)
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale-Revised (WAIS-R)	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Johnstone et al. (1999)
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale-Revised (WAIS-R) - Verbal IQ and Performance IQ	Cognitive functioning	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS) - Digit Symbol subtest	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Machamer et al. (2005)
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale (WAIS) - Performance Intelligence Quotient (PIQ)	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Machamer et al. (2005)
Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT)	Achievement	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)

Wechsler Memory Scale (WMS)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Wechsler Memory Scale-Revised (WMS-R)	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Johnstone et al. (1999)
Wechsler Memory Scale-Revised (WMS-R) - Logical Memory	Memory	TBI	LeBlanc et al. (2000)
Wide Range Ability Test	Vocational ability to determine vocational potential	Physical disabilities	D. W. Cook and Brookings (1980)
Wide Range Achievement Test (WRAT)	Achievement	Youth and adults with learning disabilities, vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010); McCue (1984)
Wide Range Achievement Test 3 (WRAT3) - Arithmetic	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Wide Range Achievement Test 4 (WRAT4)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Wide Range Achievement Test – Revised (WRAT-R) – Reading	Neuropsychological functioning	TBI	Johnstone et al. (1999)
Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST)	Neuropsychological functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Woodcock-Johnson III Tests of Achievement (WJ III ACH)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	Donoso et al. (2010); McCabe et al. (2013)
Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Cognitive Abilities (WJ-III)	Program effectiveness	Various disabilities	McCabe et al. (2013)
Woodcock-Johnson Tests of Cognitive Abilities (WJ)	Cognitive functioning	Vocational rehabilitation clients	Donoso et al. (2010)
Work Adjustment Rating Form (WARF)	Employment potential	Behavioral disabilities	Roessler and Boone (1982)
Work history interview on work readiness, work attitudes, interpersonal relations, and work quality and performance	Prediction of employment outcomes for clients in a community psychiatric	Schizophrenia, major affective disorder, and other	Bond and Friedmeyer (1987)

	rehabilitation program		
Work Locus of Control Scale (WLCS)	Self-understanding and empowerment	Not identified	Breeding (2008)
Work Orientation Questionnaire	Employment potential	Behavioral disabilities	Roessler and Boone (1982)
Work Performance Index (WPI)	Work capacity	Psychiatric disorders (schizophrenia; bipolar disorder; depression; substance abuse; psychosis)	Zarate et al. (1998)
Work-Interest Profile for Rehabilitation Counseling (WIPRC)	Self-understanding and empowerment	Not identified	Breeding (2008)

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